

THE DETERMINATION OF JOB SATISFACTION LEVEL OF THE INDIVIDUALS WORKING IN PRIVATE SPORTS INSTITUTION – THE MACFİT EXAMPLE

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Özet:

Araştırmanın amacı, özel spor merkezlerinde çalışan personelin, iş doyum düzeylerinin bazı değişkenlere göre değerlendirilmesidir. Araştırmada veri toplama yöntemi olarak nicel araştırma yöntemi, araştırmanın amacı doğrultusunda veri elde etmek amacıyla anket uygulanmıştır. Araştırmanın evreni İstanbul ili Macfitt çalışanları (n=270) pe oluştururken örnekleme ise kolayda örnekleme yöntemi ile İstanbul Avrupa Yakası Macfite çalışan 171 gönüllü personel oluşturmaktadır. Araştırmada Balcı'nın (1999) geliştirdiği İş Doyumu Ölçeği kullanılmıştır. Ölçek altı demografik soru, 34 beşli likert sordandan oluşmaktadır. Yapılan Kolmogorov-Smirnov Testi sonucunda veriler, homojen dağılım göstermediği tespit edildi. Katılımcıların cinsiyeti ile iş doyum puan ortalamalarına göre yapılan Mann-Whitney U testi analizinde anlamlı bir farklılık gözlenmemiştir. Yaş grubunda farklılık olduğunu belirlemek amacıyla yapılan ANOVA testinde; 18-25 yaş aralığı ile 26-33 yaş aralığı personellerin iş doyum puanının daha yüksek olduğu anlaşılmıştır. Eğitim durumunda farklılık olduğunu belirlemek amacıyla yapılan ANOVA testinde; lisans mezunu personellerin iş doyum puanının daha yüksek olduğu anlaşılmıştır.. Katılımcıların hizmet yılı ile iş doyum puan ortalamalarına göre yapılan Kruskal Wallis testi analizinde anlamlı bir farklılık gözlenmemiştir. Sonuç olarak, 18 – 25 yaş aralığı çalışan Macfit personelinin iş doyum düzeylerinde anlamlı farklılık bulunmuştur. Lisans eğitimi alan personelin iş doyum düzeylerinde anlamlı bir farklılık bulunmuştur. Cinsiyet, kurumda çalışma yılları, sahip oldukları ünvanları, kulüplere göre görev yapan personelin iş doyum düzeylerinde anlamlı bir farklılık bulunmamıştır.

Anahtar Sözcükler: spor merkezleri, iş doyum, kurumsallık

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Abstract:

The purpose of this research is the evaluation of the job satisfaction levels of the staff that works in private sports centers with respect to some variables. As the data collection method quantitative research technique, a questionnaire is carried out, to obtain data in line with the purpose of the research, The population of the research consists of Macfit employees in İstanbul province (n=270), while its sample, by using convenience sampling method, consists of 171 volunteer Macfit employees who work on the European side of İstanbul province. Job Satisfaction Scale, which is developed by Balcı (1999) is used. The scale consists of 6 demographic questions and 34 five-point Likert scale questions. It is determined that the data did not have homogeneous distribution as a result of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test that has been done. No significant difference has been observed in the Mann-Whitney U test, which is done according to participants' gender along with their job satisfaction point average. In the ANOVA test, which is done to determine that there is a difference in the age group, it is understood that job satisfaction points of 18-25 age range and 26-33 age range are higher. In the ANOVA test, which is done to determine the difference in educational status, it is understood that staff with bachelor's degree has a higher job satisfaction point. In the analyses of Kruskal Wallis test, which is done according to participants' years of service and job satisfaction point average, no significant difference is observed. As a conclusion, a significant difference has been found out in the job satisfaction levels of working Macfit personnel who has an age range of 18-25. A significant difference has been found out in the job satisfaction levels of the staff who receive an undergraduate education. No significant difference has been found in the job satisfaction levels of the staff according to their gender, years of service, titles, and clubs.

Keywords: sports centers, job satisfaction, institutionalism

1. Introduction

Nowadays, sports activities can be done in a lot of structures and area. For this reason, today many structures, may be considered as sports facilities for reasons such as the variety of sporting activities and accordingly changing nature of sports applications (Sunay, 2009). The concept of sports facility is used to define all kinds of sports area that producing sports service, designated for this purpose and equipped in accordance with. Sports services are considered as one of the important parts that are forming the sports industry and sports facilities that sporting events are done, are also included as an important element in sports services (Katırcı, 2012). The concept of sports facilities can be defined as all kinds of structures (stadium, track, field, hall, velodrome, etc.) where sports activities are done in. In other words, sports facilities are places that sports activities are done and that offer services to athletes and sports lovers (Güçlü, 1998).

Sports facilities are the structures fields and areas that have the units for sports activities, that are suitable to make unique work and preparatory training of each sport branch, national and international competitions, and to meet the needs (field, bleachers, shower, locker room, etc.) of athletes and the audience before and during the sports activities (Ramazanoğlu and Öcalan 2005).

Job satisfaction, in general, describes the joy and happiness that people receive from their job and factors related to it. In other words, job satisfaction is a collection of a person's work-related emotional responses (Koustelios 2001). When job satisfaction is high; desired outcomes by the organization such as high efficiency, reduction of absenteeism and turnover rates, increasing dedication occur (Çetinkaya and Özbaşaran, 2004).

In the service sector as in other sectors, the managers should understand and analyze the factors affecting job satisfaction levels of workers in order to improve the effectiveness and productivity of human resources, and to overcome such problems that reduce the production performance and quality as leaving employment, absenteeism and job disrupting (Karlı and Koçak, 2004). One of the most important tasks of sports administrators and developers in today and the future will be to protect the public interest in sports and sporting events. The most basic way to protect this interest is to be able to meet the expectations and needs of sports consumers (Katırcı and Oyman, 2011) It is intended to contribute to the business and to make the individuals more useful to the institution by determining the job satisfaction levels of personnel who work in private sports centers, with prioritizing the characteristics like individuality, gender, work experience, education level, organizational factors, job quality, wages promotion and working conditions. Mars Sportif has focused on new gym concept MACFİT since 2011, offering outstanding service at affordable prices. The goal is to provide to the members fun and exciting clubs prepared in high-quality standards with the appropriate sports price.

2. Methods and Tools

2.1 Research Group

The population of the study consists of 270 staff working in Istanbul in Macfit, the creating sample consists of 171 personnel working in Istanbul European Side MacFit. The limitations of this study consist of the staff working in the European Side MacFit sports centers.

2.2 Data Collection Tool

The Job Satisfaction Scale developed in 1999 by Balcı was used in this research. One of the non-probability sampling models the convenience sampling model is used in this research. The survey, implemented with the aim of job satisfaction, consists of six demographic information questions as gender, age, education level, years of service, title and the club worked in and, consists of 34 questions with five-point Likert scale as

(1) Never disagree, (2) Very Rare Agree, (3) Sometimes I agree, (4) Most of the time I agree, (5) Always Agree.

3. Findings

H1. There is a significant difference in job satisfaction level of participants' according to the gender variable.

	Gender	N	Mean	Standard deviation	Significance level
Job satisfaction	Female	57	1,67	,473	,334
	Male	114			

A significant difference was not observed according to the Mann-Whitney U test analysis made with participants' gender and job satisfaction mean scores.

H2. There is a significant difference in job satisfaction level of participants' according to the age variable.

	Age	N	Mean	Standard deviation	Significance level
Job satisfaction	18 – 25	60	2,05	1,039	,003
	26 – 33	65			
	34 – 41	30			
	41 – 49	10			
	51 and Above	6			

A significant difference was observed according to the Kruskal-Wallis test analysis made with participants' age and job satisfaction mean scores. In the ANOVA test that was performed to determine which age groups have the differences, 18-25 and 26-33 age range personnel is understood to have higher job satisfaction scores.

H3. There is a significant difference in job satisfaction level of participants' according to the education variable.

	Education level	N	Mean	Standard deviation	Significance level
Job satisfaction	Primary School	30	2,96	1,255	,05
	High School	36			
	Associate Degree	26			
	Undergraduate	68			
	Postgraduate	11			

A significant difference was observed according to the Kruskal-Wallis test analysis made with participants' education level and job satisfaction mean scores. In the

ANOVA test that was performed to determine which education level group has the difference, graduate degree personnel is understood to have higher job satisfaction scores.

H4. There is a significant difference in job satisfaction level of participants' according to the years of service in the organization variable.

	Years of service	N	Mean	Standard deviation	Significance level
Job satisfaction	1-3 years	30	1,19	,642	,718
	4-6 years	36			
	7-9 years	26			
	10 years and more	68			

A significant difference was not observed according to the Kruskal-Wallis test analysis made with participants' years of service and job satisfaction mean scores.

H5. There is a significant difference in job satisfaction level of participants' according to the title variable

	Title	N	Mean	Standard deviation	Significance level
Job satisfaction	District Manager	4	5,53	1,562	,104
	Club Manager	8			
	Club Deputy Manager	10			
	Sales Manager	10			
	Sales Consultant	30			
	Fitness Instructor	63			
	Club Cleaning Staff	40			
	Technical Officer	6			

A significant difference was not observed according to the Kruskal-Wallis test analysis made with participants' title and job satisfaction mean scores.

H6. There is a significant difference in job satisfaction level of participants' according to the club worked in variable

	Sport clubs	N	Mean	Standard deviation	Significance level
Job satisfaction	Akbati	10	9,65	5,499	,000
	Akatlar	12			
	Ataköy	17			
	Bakirköy	11			
	Bayrampaşa	7			
	Fulya	5			
	212 Avm	3			
	Kağıthane	3			
	Marmarapark	19			
	Maslak	4			
	Merter	13			
	Ortaköy	11			
	Ömür	12			
	Özdilek	16			
	Torium	8			
	Tramp	17			
Vieland	3				

A significant difference was observed according to the Kruskal-Wallis test analysis made with participants' club worked in and job satisfaction mean scores.

4. Conclusion and Discussion

In this study, significant differences were examined in job satisfaction levels of the staff of the Istanbul province Macfit sports club located on the European side, according to their age, educational level and total years of service. A significant difference was not detected in the Mann-Whitney U test analysis carried out in the study according to the mean score of participants' gender and job satisfaction (see table H1).

A significant difference was not observed according to the Kruskal-Wallis test analysis made with participants' title and job satisfaction mean scores. In the research conducted on 300 workers by Yelboğa (2007), in order to determine the relationship between individual demographic variables and job satisfaction, a significant difference was not found in the scores of job satisfaction according to staff's mission in the institution. A significant difference was observed according to the Kruskal-Wallis test analysis made with participants' club worked in and job satisfaction mean scores.

According to the results of the analysis, a significant difference was observed according to the Kruskal-Wallis test analysis made with participants' age and job satisfaction mean scores. In the ANOVA test that was performed to determine which age groups have the differences, 18-25 and 26-33 age range personnel is understood to have higher job satisfaction scores. (See table H2). Uyar in 2013 has reached out the conclusion that between the age groups workers in the range of 18-21 years of age have the highest job satisfaction whereas workers who are 38 years old and older, age group have the lowest job satisfaction according to the age parameter. In the study conducted

between 190 personnel working in the General Directorate of Youth and Sports Headquarter by Demir (2002), to determine job satisfaction, it has been found that individuals between the ages of 20-30 have the highest job satisfaction whereas individuals between the ages of 31-40 has the lowest job satisfaction in terms of wage subscale.

When related literature is examined, in outcomes, according to the results of the analysis done with education level variables, in the organizational environment size, there was no significant difference between the views of staff in terms of education level variable. A significant difference was observed among the participants the ones who received an undergraduate degree in our study, according to the Kruskal-Wallis test analysis made with participants' education level and job satisfaction mean scores. Uyar in 2013 has found that, according to the education level, the level of job satisfaction is higher among the workers who had received undergraduate degree education level than the ones who had received primary school degree education level, in terms of job qualification subscale. In the ANOVA test that was conducted to determine which education level has the difference, the job satisfaction scores of undergraduate staff were found to be higher (See table H3).

A significant difference was not observed according to the Kruskal-Wallis test analysis made with participants' years of service, which is 1–3 years, and job satisfaction mean scores. A significant difference was not observed according to the Kruskal-Wallis test analysis made with participants' title and job satisfaction mean scores. Uyar in 2013, there is a significant difference between the people who work 1-3 years and 4-6 years according to the years of service in the sports center, they worked for and in terms of work colleague subscale. A significant difference was observed according to the Kruskal-Wallis test analysis made with participants' club worked in and job satisfaction mean scores. In terms of colleague subscale, the reason for the higher job satisfaction level of 1-3 years staff than 4-6 years staff may be because of; people who work 1-3 years, have forward-looking expectations and goals, and are still in the learning phase of the job and functioning of processes and organizational culture and the familiarization phase of the work and colleagues.

4.1 Suggestions

In determining job satisfaction level, the wage is one of the most important consideration. When Macfit's working conditions are taken into consideration, the company does not provide any salary for the fitness instructors, however, 100% of the sales of private lessons is left to the fitness trainer. Apart from that, if fitness instructors are given symbolic figure wages according to the number of the group that they give lessons to, the job satisfaction level of the fitness trainer can be satisfied.

One of the other considerations in determining the job satisfaction level is the level of education. When table H3 is examined in our study, it is showed that the job satisfaction level of the staff with undergraduate education is high. The job satisfaction

level of the staff with primary school, high school, and associate degree education level can be increased with various training and organizations.

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